

Evaluation of Egg Shells in Wallpaper Production

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Abstract

Wallpaper is pasted in vertical strips over the walls of rooms, offices, restaurants, hospitals, hotels etc. to provide a decorative surface. In this study, the radiation reduction effect of waste egg shells was investigated in order to reduce the radiation, especially in offices and hospitals. Writing and printing papers were used as balance (base) paper in wallpaper production and its physical and optical properties were determined. Base papers have been coated with mixtures of precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) and egg shell calcium carbonate (ECC) at certain rates. In order to improve water resistance of wallpaper, PVA (polyvinyl acetate) was applied on the surface of the dried wallpapers in the conditioning room. The physical and optical of the papers were investigated to compare with each other.

The results show that the whiteness values of the wallpaper increased with using PCC while decreased with using ECC. The brightness and yellowness values decreased not significantly and the physical properties of the wallpapers have decreased with coating process. As a result, waste egg shells were evaluated as a new raw material and water resistant wallpapers were produced.

Key Words: Wallpaper, ECC, PCC

1. Introduction

The wallpaper is made up of two lapped paper layers. The first one is the unprinted base (balance) paper, the other one is the printed surface paper. There are 7 different surface types on the wallpaper: paper, fiber, textile, emboss, vinyl, heavy vinyl and natural materials. There are also 3 types of base paper: paper, fiber, textile (URL-1). Wallpapers are a visual building material that is applied as proper to personal taste on interior walls. Writing-printing papers have 60-80 grammages and are suitable for writing and printing. The structure of the paper consists of chemical cellulose or chemical cellulose and mechanical wood pulp mixture. Coating is also applied to paper based on its usage area (URL-2; Yakut, 2012).

Precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) is synthetically produced by chemical precipitation of limestone and has many outstanding properties such as high CaCO_3 content, low impurity ratio, diversity of crystal structure and possibility of being produced in homogeneous grain size distribution. PCC can be used as a filling material for high quality, strength paper production, as well as on surface as coating pigment (Tutus and et al., 2012; URL-3).

It is possible to obtain calcium carbonate (ECC) from egg shells after removing membranes, drying, grinding and sieving. The purity grade of the obtained ECC is approximately 93.7% (Killi, 2017; URL-4).

In this study, the usability of PCC and ECC in the wallpaper production was investigated and effects of PCC and ECC on the physical and optical properties of the wallpapers were determined.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Material

Writing-printing papers used in this study as base paper with 80 grammages were taken from Kombassan Paper Inc.; PCC as coating pigment was supplied from Adacal Industrial Minerals Inc.; carboxyl methyl cellulose (CMC), starch, glitter and PVA were bought from market.

2.2. Preparation of Coating Suspensions

PCC, ECC, and starch were prepared as separate suspensions at specific concentrations for preparing the coating suspensions. The prepared suspensions were mixed to a homogeneous state in a beaker based on the ratios given in Table 1. PCC and ECC ratios were changed and 12 different coating experiments (including non-coated paper) shown in same table were performed. To determine effects of PVA on the wallpaper properties, PVA application was also carried out on the papers which were coated under the same conditions.

Table 1. Coating suspension recipes

	CaCO₃ (%)	PCC (%)	ECC (%)	CMC (%)	Starch (%)	Glitter (%)
Control	-	-	-	-	-	-
100P	82.7	100	0	0.3	13	4
90P+10E	82.7	90	10	0.3	13	4
80P+20E	82.7	80	20	0.3	13	4
70P+30E	82.7	70	30	0.3	13	4
60P+40E	82.7	60	40	0.3	13	4
50P+50E	82.7	50	50	0.3	13	4
40P+60E	82.7	40	60	0.3	13	4
30P+70E	82.7	30	70	0.3	13	4
20P+80E	82.7	20	80	0.3	13	4
10P+90E	82.7	10	90	0.3	13	4
100E	82.7	0	100	0.3	13	4

The prepared coating suspensions were applied to the paper surfaces by coating rod (no.2) three times. The coated papers were conditioned at 23±1 °C and 65±1% relative humidity in a conditioning room and then subjected to calendering at 25 °C under 15 bar pressures.

2.3. Physical and Optical Tests

Coated wallpapers were subjected to the physical and optical properties in order to determine effects of PCC, ECC and PVA on these properties. The physical and optical tests applied to wallpaper were given in Table 2 with relevant standards.

Table 2. The physical and optical tests applied to coated paper

Physical and Optical Tests	Standarts
Breaking length	TAPPI T494 om-01
Tear index	TAPPI T414 om-12
Burst index	TAPPI T403 om-15
Thickness	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Density	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Bulkiness	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Brightness	ISO 2469:2014
Whiteness	ISO 2469:2014
Yellowness	ASTM E313
Opacity	TAPPI T 519 om-02
Cobb ₃₀	TAPPI T 441 om-04

*Machine and cross directions averages were used for breaking length and tear index

Three replicates were done for each experiment, and mean values were used to determine the physical and optical properties of the coated papers.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. The Physical and Optical Properties of the Wallpapers

Table 3 and 4 show test results of the physical properties of the coated wallpapers with PVA and PVA-free such as breaking length, burst and tear indices, bulkiness and density depending on PCC and ECC ratios.

Table 3. The physical properties of the PVA-free coated wallpapers

	Breaking length (km)	Burst index (kPa.m ² /g)	Tear index (mN.m ² /g)	Cobb ₃₀ (gr/m ²)	Bulkiness (cm ³ /g)	Density (g/cm ³)
Control	4.00	3.12	6.39	83	1.25	0.80
100P	3.26	2.66	4.55	105	1.15	0.87
90P+10E	3.37	2.68	5.16	105	1.34	0.75
80P+20E	3.36	2.69	5.75	103	1.39	0.72
70P+30E	3.01	2.35	5.32	101	1.52	0.66
60P+40E	3.08	2.45	5.99	100	1.47	0.68
50P+50E	3.27	2.62	4.20	93	1.51	0.66
40P+60E	3.05	2.48	5.24	100	1.46	0.68
30P+70E	3.15	2.52	5.51	98	1.61	0.62
20P+80E	3.15	2.71	5.63	96	1.60	0.62
10P+90E	3.26	2.50	5.89	111	1.60	0.63
100E	2.96	2.42	5.41	116	1.54	0.65

*P: PCC, E: ECC

Table 4. The physical properties of the coated wallpapers applied PVA

	Breaking length (km)	Burst index (kPa.m ² /g)	Tear index (mN.m ² /g)	Cobb ₃₀ (gr/m ²)	Bulkiness (cm ³ /g)	Density (g/cm ³)
Control	4.00	3.12	6.39	83	1.24	0.80
100P	3.31	2.50	5.79	84	1.29	0.78
90P+10E	3.12	2.73	6.73	85	1.41	0.71
80P+20E	3.00	2.49	4.48	98	1.51	0.66
70P+30E	3.42	2.32	5.25	84	1.52	0.66
60P+40E	3.25	2.76	4.98	87	1.53	0.65
50P+50E	3.05	2.23	4.95	88	1.53	0.65
40P+60E	3.31	2.64	5.74	87	1.55	0.65
30P+70E	3.06	2.47	4.94	83	1.55	0.65
20P+80E	3.28	2.50	5.41	88	1.59	0.63
10P+90E	3.03	2.61	4.98	93	1.62	0.62
100E	2.81	2.39	5.66	95	1.65	0.61

It has been clearly seen that the physical properties of the coated papers were significantly reduced. When fibers interact with coating pigments, the fiber-fiber bond reduces as well as paper strength (Eroglu and Usta, 2004; Karademir and et al., 2013). With PCC and ECC as coating pigment, the breaking lengths of the coated wallpapers decreased about 18.5% and 26%, respectively when compared with non-coated papers. Also, the Cobb₃₀ values, burst and tear indices of the wallpaper have been affected negatively (Fig. 1 and 2). In many studies, it has been found that the use of pigments such as CaCO₃ in the coating process has a negative effect on the physical properties of the papers. Tutus et al. (2012) found that the use of PCC (0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100%) as filler during paper production reduced the physical properties of the paper.

Figure 1. The physical properties of the PVA-free coated wallpapers

Figure 2. The physical properties of the coated wallpapers applied PVA

Tutus et al., (2013) reported that the physical properties of the waste papers were reduced with using PCC as filler in paper production. In this study they also compared the effects of PCC and GCC on optical and physical properties of the papers. Due to controlled production of PCC and its regular grain size and shape and size distribution, it has been seen that the physical properties of the papers are negligibly reduced when compared with GCC.

When PCC and ECC are compared to each other, the breaking length and burst index values are better for PCC and tear index values are better for ECC. Parallel to the increase in the ECC ratio in the coating suspension, bulkiness values increased while the density value decreased. While there was no significant effect on physical properties with the use of PVA, there was improvement in COBB value due to PVA's water repellency.

The optical properties of the coated wallpapers applied PVA and PVA-free were given in Table 5 and 6.

Table 5. The optical properties of the PVA-free coated wallpapers

	ISO Whiteness (%)	ISO Brightness (%)	Yellowness (E 313)	ISO Opacity(%)
Control	80.52	100.13	-29.51	96.62
100P	82.41	94.70	-16.91	97.53
90P+10E	82.71	92.86	-14.80	98.41
80P+20E	82.59	93.71	-16.33	97.32
70P+30E	82.69	92.46	-14.27	98.12
60P+40E	81.97	94.09	-17.62	97.38
500P+50E	82.71	93.54	-15.77	97.21
40P+60E	81.77	91.21	-13.92	97.07
30P+70E	81.44	92.72	-16.59	98.00
20P+80E	80.65	94.12	-20.27	97.32
10P+90E	79.81	92.41	-18.94	95.81
100E	79.74	92.84	-19.68	99.80

Table 6. The optical properties of the coated wallpapers applied PVA

	ISO Whiteness (%)	ISO Brightness (%)	Yellowness (E 313)	ISO Opacity(%)
Control	80.52	100.13	-29.51	96.62
100P	81.74	94.14	-18.39	97.26
90P+10E	82.15	94.45	-17.63	96.56
80P+20E	82.01	93.93	-17.71	97.97
70P+30E	81.49	92.88	-16.82	97.22
60P+40E	82.05	93.14	-16.34	98.11
500P+50E	82.07	94.82	-18.77	97.44
40P+60E	81.69	91.24	-14.06	97.44
30P+70E	81.33	94.56	-17.86	97.67
20P+80E	80.25	94.05	-20.67	98.39
10P+90E	79.55	95.35	-23.64	96.11
100E	79.86	91.70	-17.84	98.07

It has been observed that the whiteness value has increased and the brightness value has decreased with using PCC as coating pigment. With using ECC, these values have reduced. When compared with ECC, PCC provides better whiteness and brightness values due to its whiter and brighter structure. Generally, PCC and GCC have a whiter structure than paper. The whiteness value of CaCO_3 in PCC varies between 95% and 98% (Ozden, 1988; Koltka and Sabah, 2012). Due to its transparent structure, there is no significant effect of PVA on the optical properties of the coated wallpapers. Yoo et al. (2009) used ECC particles as coating pigments in writing-printing paper coating and investigated its effect on ink density and optical properties of the papers. As coating pigments, the addition of ECC particles has increased the ink density and optical density of blue, magenta and yellow inks, which reduces the brightness of the coated papers.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The physical and optical properties of the paper need to be known in order to determine its suitability for its usage area. Especially for wallpapers to be printed, it is expected that the properties such as surface smoothness, whiteness and ink absorbency are better. As a result of this study, it is seen that PCC and ECC have negative effects on the physical properties of the wallpapers applied PVA and PVA-free. Cobb value of the wallpaper applied PVA was found to be better than that of PVA-free wallpapers. In the optical properties, the whiteness increased with using PCC, but decreased with ECC. Although there is no significant difference between

the opacity values, opaque papers have been obtained as a result of the reduction of gaps between the fibers with the use of ECC. As a result of this study;

1. ECC (60% ECC) can be used with PCC based on physical properties in wallpaper production.
2. ECC can be used up to 40% as coating pigment in wallpaper production that is the foreground of the whiteness in terms of optical properties.
3. The increase in the use of ECC is thought to be helpful in the production of wallpaper with the emboss technique.
4. The use of waste egg shells in the wallpaper production will reduce the damage to the environment and enable the production of high added value products.

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